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Impact of Quality Hrm Practices on Job Satisfaction, Evidence from University Employees of Pakistan

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Abstract

Successful and winning companies are those that value their human capital as their most important asset. Human Resources Management (HRM) is the planned management of the employees, who independently and together take for the achievement of the strategic goals and objectives of the organization. HRM functions as the connection between the organization and the employees. HRM Practices are known as important factors of employees' performance. The core idea of this study is to examine the association between HRM Practices on Employee Job Satisfaction in public sector universities of Pakistan. Data has been composed from the employees of various public sector universities with the help of a questionnaire. The result has been analyzed and recommendation has been made based on analysis.

Keywords: Quality Hrm Practices, Job Satisfaction

1. Introduction: HRM is defined as the process of hiring and development of the employees to become more important assets of the organization. HRM practices mean Job Analysis, Succession Planning for individual employees, recruiting the appropriate person according to Job Description, orientation of newly hired employees and training where necessary, managing the pay scales and wages, rewarding financially and non-financially, monitoring performance, handling disruption and resolving disputes and sharing the information with employees.

HRM play a vital role to manage employee activities individually and collectively in an organization. HRM is a bridge between management and employees to operate the organizational functions. By using HRM practices organizational objectives and outcomes can be measure, focuses and achieved. What this means is that the HR function in contemporary organizations is concerned with the notions of people enabling, people development and a focus on maintaining the "employment relationship" satisfying the management and employees as well.

The most widely accepted explanation of job satisfaction was presented by Locke (1976), who defined job satisfaction as “a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one’s job or job experiences”. Additionally, job satisfaction has emotional, cognitive and behavioral components (Bernstein & Nash, 2008).

The emotional component refers to feelings regarding the job, such as boredom, anxiety, or excitement. The cognitive component of job satisfaction refers to beliefs regarding one's job, for example, feeling that one's job is mentally demanding and challenging. Finally, the behavioral component includes people's actions in relation to their work. These actions may include being tardy, staying late, or pretending to be ill in order to avoid work (Bernstein & Nash, 2008). Low job satisfaction can cause a low morale which will cause the employee to work fewer and concentrate more on the negative aspects of the job.

As a person the employee will feel unhappy and this depression will reach to his friends and family. People around him are to be expected to feel the disturbance and may even have to bear the impact of it from time to time. People who are not satisfied with jobs can have major problems in their individual and personal relationships. In many cases as ad worker may hold marital problems and health problems caused by pressure and stress. Looking at it from an employer's viewpoint, there will be a sharp decrease in output. Again, a person who is not contented with his job will see that his relationships with people at work will begin to undergo causing inter personal problems at job.

There will be no scope for growth which will make things worse. The main goals / responsibilities of HRM are:

- To keep low employee turnover rate by inspiring employees to work for the company
- To catch the attention of new employees
- To contribute to employee growth and development currently, organizations can stay alive in the dynamic, competitive and hostile environment of today only if they take advantage of the full potential of each employee. Unfortunately, a lot of companies have not understood the significance of the human capital in successful processes and operations. The employment and selection of the superlative employees is a very difficult obligation.

Why employees at some companies are pleased to be attached with the company while others are looking for alternative employment? The reason is that some companies know how to take care of its employees’ superior and provide a favorable environment for the work that will help them to retain their identity, while showing themselves and the hard work and growing along with the company. Sullivan (2012) has defined some best HR practices that help in the creation of a highly satisfied and motivated work force.

1. Interacting with employees on social media
2. Contest –Games become part of the workplace
3. Social gathering once in a Month
4. Appraising on customer receipts
5. Contests for attracting passives
6. Remote college Immersing managers in day-to-day reality
7. Simulations for assessment
8. “Why do you stay” retention interviews
9. Forget resumes, watch them work
10. Open-office design improves decision-making speed To that ending,

HRM is very vital for the whole function of an organization because it helps the organization to make loyal employees, who are prepared to offer their best for the company. The universities contribute a key role in financial and social development of any country. The employee's contribute in management of universities. Job satisfaction is a topic of wide interest to both people who work in institutes and people who study them. Administration and manager tries their level best to create conducive environment for the employees in whom they feel pleasure. The satisfaction of employee's in Universities is significant for performance and nationwide education system that eventually effect on state growth. So it is vital to know their behavior and approach to make them satisfy and to boost obligation. There are many factors that persuade satisfaction of the employees both in developed and developing countries. Researcher have examined the relationship of satisfaction between with promotion, pay, working condition, fringe benefits, support of research, appraisal, administration and staff evaluation. HRM in many organizations focuses on human capital growth and advocates the HR forecasting, performance management and staffing and selection of employees. In Pakistan, HRM is rising and moving ahead very fast day by day. Many people are attracted towards this field and there are also different HR degrees and majors in the universities and institutes. The HRM faced conflicts from top management and older employees. If there is no HR department, then the HR tasks are shared by other departments. When HR department was established, some people especially top management thought that the HR will decrease their authorities and will go ahead to conflicts. But HR in reality benefits the business and other departments of organization.

2. Problem Statement: The universities are also like an organization in Pakistan. The effects of human resource management practices on job satisfaction of University employees will be discussed in this study in detail. The focus is on impact of HRM Practices on job satisfaction of employees in universities of Pakistan.

3. Literature Review: HRM Practices are associated with the management of human resources, activities essential for staffing the business and maintaining the high employee performance (Mahmood, 2004). The most general HR Practices include succession planning, recruitment, selection, training and development, compensation, employees and labour relations, rewards and recognition (Yeganeh, 2008). Dessler (2007) described six HRM practices selective hiring, recognition, compensation policy, rewards, training and development and information sharing; those have been studied with connection to employee job satisfaction.

Job satisfaction can be defined as an employee's overall affective condition resulting from an agreement of all aspects of his/her job. An employee's level of satisfaction to her/his job differs with specific aspects of the job. Many studies and researches have demonstrated that job satisfaction is one of the major key factors of individual and organizational performance. In human resource management practices persons most likely have a higher level of communication with colleagues, other employees and outsiders of the organization; a larger involvement of in decision-making process. Trust, motivation and intrinsic rewards are certainly related to high job commitment and positive attitudes toward the job. Job rotation also might increase employee's job satisfaction by giving wisdom of belonging, reducing dullness, and polishing skills, needed for their promotions, Freeman and Kleiner (2000).

According to Askenazy and Caroli, HRM practices may have some direct effects on employee's job satisfaction. They argued that in the team work, worker's control according to pace of should be decreased and peer's pressure should be increased, conflicts among coworkers also reduced.

Steijn (2004) found that HRM practices put significant effect on employees' job satisfaction in term of its positivity of Dutch public sector whereas employees' individual characteristics like age, gender, and education put insignificant effect on job satisfaction.

4. Methodology: The questionnaire will be developed to inquire about the job satisfaction perspective of Human Resource Management practices from employees in the universities of Pakistan. Following aspects of HRM practices will be studied:-

1. Employees' are satisfied on "Recruitment and selection systems".
2. Employees' are satisfied on "Compensation package".
3. Employees' are satisfied on "Job security".
4. Employees' are satisfied on "Career growth".
5. Employees' are satisfied on "Training and development".
6. Employees' are satisfied on "Management style".
7. Employees' are satisfied on "Job design and responsibilities".
8. Employees' are satisfied on "Reward and motivation".
9. Employees' are satisfied on "Working environment".
10. Employees' are satisfied on "Performance appraisal system". And most important
11. "Employees' are satisfied with their jobs overall".

A questionnaire will be developed to study above mentioned queries. Questioner will be disbursed in university employees and recommendations will be made after analysis of responses.

Propositions of research: Research propositions have been developed for questions of research questionnaires. These aspects will be analyzed in detail this study. The research questionnaire will be served among the faculty members and staff of the public sector universities in Pakistan. The sample of four universities in Lahore has been taken and 200 questionnaires has been disbursed and received from employees.

5. Recruitment: Recruitment is gathering information of suitable candidates against the post advertised properly through various channels according to needs of the organization. Recruitment is a tool for filter the irrelevant candidates or data. Selection process is a technique to select appropriate person for the right job by using different type of tests and interviews with the help and approval of Senior Management. Recruitment and Selection Process needs to be set SOPs to refine and choose the very suitable candidates.

Good recruitment and selection process strategies play vital role in organizational outcomes in terms of hiring of effective and suitable candidates, especially in retention of satisfied employees of organization.

6. Remuneration Package: A remuneration package means a bundle of financial and non-financial rewards like wages, salary, family insurance, education funds, increments in salary, appreciation letters, free transportation, time relaxation, vacations, study tours and various trainings in all over the world. Companies provide all these remuneration/compensation packages for retention of their good employees. Employees who gets enrollment in higher study programmes do sing various type of bond to service the organization for a certain time period.

7. Job security: Almost all employees have many concerns about their job security, they want to measure the future chances of their unemployment and how much their job is secure.

8. Factors affecting job security: Job security business conditions, and the individual's personal skills, depending on the economy. It's a time of economic expansion and recession, more work in less time that has been found to protect. In addition, some laws (such as the 1964 Civil Rights Act) that certain illegal to fire employees for reasons of security and encourage employment.

The unemployment rate is a good indicator of job security and the economy, and economists, government officials, and is tracked by banks. Employment opportunities in the private sector generally believed to offer less job security and the industry in general, location, occupation and other factors differ from the general, government jobs and education, health public and law enforcement jobs are considered very safe. This kind of education, work experience, work functional area, job industry, job location, etc. as personal factors, an individual's need for services play an important role in determining, job security and their personal impacts. As a result of current economic conditions and job security depend on the business environment in which the required skills are in demand from employers and from experience depends on which those services are in high demand by employers work 'll enjoy are protected.

Career Growth "Career growth" or "Job advancement" usually means a change from an entry level position to a job which has more duties and that receives more compensation. For example, a company which is large enough to allow a sequence of jobs: base worker to team leader to supervisor to vice president is a company which allows "Career Development" Career development skills and commitment of its people and thrives best in return, provides training and career development opportunities - together with a highly competitive salary and benefit packages. Career development of a young, vibrant and dynamic company provides fast-track career progression and competitive salary packages to attract their business. This is the best of the industry, and construction is at the forefront of best practice that represents teams that can offer professional capacity means.

Training and Development: Training and development is a subsystem of an organization. It ensures that randomness is reduced and learning or behavioral change takes place in structured format.

It is the field which is concerned with organizational activity aimed at bettering the performance of individuals and groups in organizational settings. Training and development (T&D) encompasses three main activities: training, education, and development. Training is the activity is both focused upon, and evaluated against, the job that an individual currently holds. Development activity focuses upon the activities that the organization employing the individual, or that the individual is part of, may partake in the future, and is almost impossible to evaluate.

9. Management Styles: The styles of Management are the specific ways to take decisions about their subordinates; which are related to their progress. Styles of the Management can be classified into two major types are:-

- Autocratic,
- Democratic Style.

Autocratic (or authoritarian) managers like to make all the important decisions and closely supervise and control workers. Managers do not trust workers and simply give orders (one-way communication) that they expect to be obeyed. This approach derives from the views of Taylor as to how to motivate workers and relates to McGregor's theory X view of workers. This approach has limitations (as highlighted by other motivational theorists such as Mayo and Herzberg) but it can be effective in certain situations.

In contrast to the autocratic style, Enterprise uses democratic decision-taking in many parts of the business. Everyone has the opportunity to contribute ideas to the decision. There are two types of democratic decision-making:

1. Persuasive democratic management - here the leader makes the decision first and then persuades employees that he or she has made the right decision

2. Consultative democratic management - this involves the group contributing to the decision-making process, with the leader making the final decision

The team is central to delivering good customer service. The consultative approach helps Enterprise achieve this business objective.

10. Job Design & Responsibilities: Job Design usually involves:

Responsibilities + Job Contents + Specific Qualification

Job Design is a set of Job Responsibilities, Job Contents and required the specific qualification to do the job in the organization. It usually involved Job requirements which are essential to do the same job. In this design Managers find the right person for the right job with specific qualifications and skills related to the job. They find the right who do the job well. It also involves the technological expertise as well as the personal social requirement of the job holder. In this design managers give responsibilities to the job holder with required control over the job work and scheduling the work time to time. By applying the job design an organization gets more satisfied employees towards organization and its goals.

11. Reward System: A reward system is a system that is designed to determine amount of pay given the many individuals in an organization. On its simplest level, a manager simply makes his or her best guess as to what an individual should be paid and what he or she will accept. In its most complex form, a reward system contains many different decision, guidelines, and processes for determining pay level and pay structure.

Pay Structure- The relative pay differential among various jobs within the organization and how this is determined.

Pay Level- The relative amount of pay assigned to each job compared to the job market

Pay Form- The makeup of the pay this individual receives. The relative amount of guaranteed vs. at risk pay.

Basis for pay increases- How pay changes from year to year is an important aspect of a compensations system. The various bases for change are:

1. Seniority and longevity
2. Cost of living
3. Performance/merit
4. Changes in job scope
5. Increases in individual qualifications such as a new degree or certification.
6. Changes in market for job and/or individual- A special form of this type of increase are to match a competing job offer.

12. Performance Appraisal System: In this system the organization can measure the performance of an employee and evaluated it. Performance appraisal usually includes in the career development and contains the regular reviews of employee performance. Performance appraisal is a very systemic and on-going process that measures an individual job performance and productivity with setting-up a certain criteria and organizational goals and objectives. In performance appraisal some other aspects are also calculated like employee behavior, accomplishment of assignments, strengths and weaknesses etc. Overall Job Satisfaction Affective job satisfaction is the extent of pleasurable emotional feelings individuals have about their jobs overall, it is the extent of individuals' satisfaction with particular facets of their jobs, such as pay, pension arrangements,

working hours, and numerous other aspects of their jobs. A strategic way of achieving job satisfaction is to establish a corporate culture that encourages communication and is directed towards quality work.

13. Data Analysis Research design: The present study follows an ex-post fact of research design. The experimental design could not be used because the conditions being studied were pre-existing in the population and could not be randomly assigned or controlled by the researcher.

Population

The population relevant to the present study is the employees of four public sector universities of Lahore. These employees contain both the faculty members and administrative staff.

Sampling strategy

The research used non-probability (purposive) sampling strategy because the elements to be included in the research sample were selected on the basis of special characteristics of the respondents. Probability sampling could not be used because it was difficult to have access all elements of the population. Therefore, probability of occurrence of each of the element could not be determined or specified by the researcher.

Sample

The sample consisted of 200 employees of public sector universities (both male and female), taken from four public sector universities of Lahore. The names of the universities are:-

1. Govt. College University
2. COMSATS Institute of Information Technology
3. University of Engineering and Technology
4. University of Education Research Instrument

To achieve the objectives of the study a questionnaire was selected as survey instrument. The questionnaire was constructed in English language based on the literature review. This questionnaire was administrated personally among the employees by using purposive sampling. The main advantage of this was that that the researcher collected all the completed responses within short period of time. Completion of the entire questionnaire required approximately 4 to 5 minutes for atypical respondent.

Procedure for Data Collection

The data were collected from four public sector universities located in Lahore. Questionnaires were given to employees of the university and they were requested to give their actual responses. Instructions were given to fill up the questionnaires. Respondents were allowed to ask any thing they did not understand and were also assured that the information they were given would keep confidential and will be used for research purpose only.

In the end the respondents were appreciated and thanked for their cooperation.

Process for Data Analysis

Tabulation the questionnaires were checked by the researcher in order to develop the tables. Tables were prepared and checked. The percentages were worked out. It took several attempts by the researcher to prepare final tables with correct frequencies and percentages. Analysis Descriptive analysis was carried out once the

tabulation was completed. In the analysis, percentages were calculated. Then the researcher carried out interpretation.

15. Analysis of Results: Employees were asked that either they are satisfied with different HRM Practices carried out in their university. Satisfaction against following aspects of HRM practices were analyzed in detail and results achieved:-

1. "Recruitment and selection systems".
2. "Compensation package".
3. "Job security".
4. "Career growth".
5. "Training and development".
6. "Management style".
7. "Job design and responsibilities".
8. "Reward and motivation".
9. "Working environment".
10. "Performance appraisal system".
11. "Employees' are satisfied with their jobs overall".

The results are mentioned in conclusion. Conclusion and Recommendations Employees are the backbone of any business success and therefore, they need to be motivated and maintained in organization at all cost to aid the organization to be globally competitive in terms of providing quality products and services to the society. Employees' dissatisfaction results in turnover. Turnover is a critical human resource issue in all sectors of the economy. Turnover affects productivity, product and service quality, and profitability. The cost of replacing workers is high, finding skilled employees can be difficult, and investments in training are less secure.

The main objective was this study is to investigate the impacts of HRM Practices on employee's job satisfaction. The present study was conducted to investigate the impact HRM Practices on Job Satisfaction of university employees. The results of the study indicate following findings. Table 1: Overall Satisfaction with Job Yes 21 % No 79 % Most of the employees are not satisfied with their job overall i.e. 79 percent. Only 21 percent of the employees are agree that they are satisfied with their current job overall. Most of the employees are not satisfied with Rewards and Recognitions.

Rewards and recognition are both strongly associated with employee job satisfaction which is an indication that how important employees perceive rewards and recognition for them in the Public sector universities of Pakistan. Majority of the employees are not satisfied with performance appraisal systems, training and development opportunities, compensation packages, rewards and motivation etc.

16. Conclusions: The major findings formed the basis for formulating the recommendation. As the sample size is small so qualitative research techniques used. There is no need of developing a Hypothesis as research questionnaire has clearly defined specific questions. Qualitative research does not need.

Hypotheses are typically not formulated in qualitative research because qualitative research is conducted for description, exploration, and discovery. Instead of hypotheses, qualitative researchers pose research questions and some of these research questions even emerge as the study progresses, 4(Johnson, 2002).

17. Recommendations: Universities should commence proper performance appraisal systems which result in pay rise. Human Resource Management Department of the universities should offer extensive training and

development programs for the employees for better enrichment of the employees. Recruitment and selection process should be made very carefully according to the best ability of the employee concerned. University management should afford at least reasonable compensation to the employees. Employees should be properly trained to adopt new technology. Universities should focus on both intrinsic factor i.e. motivation and extrinsic factors of job satisfaction i.e. rewards. A university should first become responsive to the wants and needs of its employees. It must know and assess these needs in order to make its employees recognize their job as a part of their own life, and not as a routine responsibility.

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